

1 **Using Machine-Learning to Facilitate Data Extraction for Human Health Chemical**
2 **Assessments: A Proof-of-Concept Protocol**

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Key Words:

10 systematic review, systematic evidence map, hazard identification, toxicity, standardization,
11 interoperability, artificial intelligence, machine learning, FAIR data principles, open data

CRedit Statement:

12 **Michelle Angrish:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal Analysis, Resources, Supervision,
13 Project Administration, Writing – Original Draft Preparation. **Kristina A. Thayer:**
14 Conceptualization, Supervision, Methodology, Formal Analysis, Project Administration, Writing –
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21 Supervision, Writing – Reviewing and Editing. **Teresa Shannon:** Resources, Writing – Reviewing
22 and Editing. **Andrew Shapiro:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Resources, Validation,
23 Formal Analysis, Writing – Reviewing and Editing. **Michele Taylor:** Conceptualization,
24 Methodology, Writing – Reviewing and Editing. **Vickie Walker:** Conceptualization, Methodology,
25 Resources, Writing – Reviewing and Editing. **Andrew Rooney:** Conceptualization, Methodology,
26 Resources, Writing – Reviewing and Editing. **Sean Watford:** Conceptualization, Methodology,
27 Software, Resources, Validation, Formal Analysis, Supervision, Project Administration, Writing –
28 Original Draft Preparation.

29

Acknowledgements:

1 The authors would like to acknowledge Dale Hoff from US EPA Center for Computational Toxicology
2 and Exposure and Charles Schmitt from National Institute of Environmental Health Sciences for
3 insightful comments on previous versions of this protocol. The authors would also like to
4 acknowledge current US EPA scientists and SRC, Inc. for developing foundational approaches used
5 by the Provisional Peer-Reviewed Toxicity Value program. US EPA scientists include Jay Zhao,
6 Phillip Kaiser, Lucina Lizarraga, Jeff Dean, and Laura Carlson.

Data Availability and Deposition:

7 The data and/or code that support this work are will be made available in HAWC (build 0b3967cd)
8 and HERO (last updated April 3, 2024) at <https://hawc.epa.gov/assessment/100500328/>, [ORD
9 SEM PFAS 150 \(2022\) | HAWC \(epa.gov\)](https://heronet.epa.gov/heronet/index.cfm/project/page/project_id/3591), <https://hawc.epa.gov/assessment/100500328/>, and
10 https://heronet.epa.gov/heronet/index.cfm/project/page/project_id/3591, respectively.
11 The Environmental Health Vocabulary is available at: <https://hawc.epa.gov/vocab/ehv/>
12 3rd Party Tools including the software applications Dextr (LaserAI beta version 1.1.0), SWIFT
13 Review (V1.43), and SWIFT Active Screener (V1.061.0794) are licensed applications.

Funding and Disclaimer:

14 The authors declare they have potential competing financial interests. The views expressed are
15 those of the authors and do not necessarily represent the views or policies of the US Environmental
16 Protection Agency. Any mention of trade names, products, or services does not imply an
17 endorsement by the US Government or the US Environmental Protection Agency. Funding was
18 provided by institutional affiliation salary support. Laser AI software and support was procured
19 through order number 68HE0B23P0279.

ABSTRACT

1 **Background:**

2 Systematic review (SR) methods are relied upon to develop transparent, unbiased, and
3 standardized human health chemical assessments. The expectation is that these assessments will
4 have discovered and evaluated all of the available information in a trackable, transparent, and
5 reproducible manner inherent to SR principles. The challenge is that chemical assessment
6 development relies on mostly literature-based data using manual approaches that are not scalable.
7 Various SR tools have increased the efficiency of assessment development by implementing semi-
8 automated approaches (human in the loop) for data discovery (literature search and screening) and
9 enhanced data repositories with standardized data collection and curation frameworks. Yet filling
10 these repositories with data extractions has remained a manual process and connecting the various
11 tools together in one interoperable workflow remains challenging.

12 **Objectives:** The objective of this protocol is to explore incorporation of a semi-automated data
13 extraction tool (Dextr) into a chemical assessment workflow and understand if the new tool
14 improves overall user experience.

15 **Methods:** The workflow will use template Systematic Evidence Map (SEM) methods developed by
16 the Environmental Protection Agency for the identification of included studies. The methods
17 described focus on the data extraction component of the workflow using a fully manual or a semi-
18 automated (human in the loop) data extraction approach. Both the manual and semi-automated
19 data extractions will occur in Dextr. The new data extraction tool will be evaluated for user
20 experience and whether the data extracted using the automated approach meets or exceeds metrics
21 (precision, recall, and F1 score) for a fully manual data extraction.

22 **Discussion**

23 Artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) methods have rapidly advanced and show
24 promise in achieving operational efficiencies in chemical assessment workflows by supporting
25 automated or semi-automated SR methods, possibly improving the user experience. Yet
26 incorporating advances into sustainable workflows has remained a challenge. Whether using a tool
27 like Dextr improves operational efficiencies and the user experience remains to be determined.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

1 The field of chemical assessment is an essential component of public health, aimed at
2 evaluating the hazards associated with environmental exposure for the purpose of protecting
3 human and environmental health. The Environmental Protection Agency's Chemical Pollutant
4 Assessment Division (CPAD) is tasked with developing various human health assessments that
5 evaluate all of the available information in a manner that is trackable, transparent, and unbiased.
6 CPAD has made significant advancements in assessment development processes by implementing
7 standardized workflows and tools that increase the efficiency of information review and
8 management (U.S. EPA, 2022) (Figure 1). A major challenge to assessment development has been
9 scaling traditional assessment approaches to meet the rate that information is made available and
10 organizing/sorting/labeling that information once it has been found. For example, PubMed covers
11 approximately 26,000 journals and contains approximately 36 million citations (accessed March
12 27, 2024).

13 Advantageously, as technological advances have improved access to information, they have
14 also advanced the methods, tools, and database management systems that assessment developers
15 use for finding and evaluating information. Use of tools, with auditing capability, that are web
16 accessible, support asynchronous collaboration, and use computationally intelligent approaches are
17 required to meet the demand for efficient and rapid development of systematic reviews (SR) and
18 systematic evidence maps (SEMs) (Thayer et al., 2022; Thayer et al., 2023). While these tools
19 currently lack full automation and require a human in the loop, up and coming artificial intelligence
20 (AI) move us toward it. The expectation is that moving toward automation using AI models will
21 help address the increasing demand to rapidly extract the information informing assessments while
22 adhering to foundational systematic (evidence mapping) methods. The workflows could be
23 scalable and include the elasticity needed to rapidly scale (up or down) and reuse previous work in
24 alignment with FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) (Wilkinson et. al.,
25 2016).

26 To date, the machine learning (ML)-assisted workflows implemented with SR tools and
27 similar applications have principally eased the human burden by decreasing the amount of time
28 spent screening studies at the title and abstract (TiAB) level, resulting in a significant reduction in

1 overall time and costs associated with screening reviewed by (Van der Mierde et. al., 2019). While
2 these tools can facilitate the screening phase, they are not yet capable of automating the entire
3 process, which includes complex tasks like data extraction and evidence synthesis. Therefore,
4 summarizing the information available for decisions is still a challenge because existing tools still
5 heavily rely upon manual user manipulation at each point in the workflow. Further, assessment
6 teams in general lack software developers and therefore the coding knowledge required to write
7 applications related to any form of large language model processing/AI. There are some tools with
8 user interfaces that require little to no coding knowledge, but interoperability gaps exist meaning
9 that coding knowledge is still required to migrate data between tool APIs. These gaps highlight
10 further the institutional barriers to acquiring the needed infrastructure for hosting all the
11 information technology (IT) components to fully enable intelligent document and data processing
12 workflows. Therefore, assessment teams must partner with coding experts and their institutions to
13 develop an ecosystem for developing the requirements needed for an intelligent document
14 processing workflow, while providing training data needed by coders to refine ML models.

15 Developing ML models for literature screening and data extraction poses several additional
16 challenges. First, research involves a vast and diverse literature that spans multiple scientific
17 disciplines, making it challenging to identify and extract relevant information. Second, many studies
18 use complex methodologies, technical jargon, and highly specialized terminology, which can be
19 difficult for ML algorithms to comprehend. Additionally, the lack of standardized language and
20 terminology used in research can hinder the development of accurate ML models. Third, the quality
21 of the available data can be highly variable, and the data may be biased or incomplete, which can
22 lead to inaccurate results and therefore models. Fourth, the interpretation of results often requires
23 a high level of domain expertise, making it challenging to validate the performance of ML models by
24 human experts. Finally, ethical considerations, such as ensuring privacy and protecting sensitive
25 information, must be carefully considered when developing ML models for any field, but
26 environmental/biomedical text used to support decisions. Addressing these challenges will require
27 the integration of domain expertise, data quality control, and a collaborative effort between
28 computer scientists and environmental health researchers to develop robust and reliable ML
29 models for literature screening and data extraction in environmental chemical research.

1 In this paper, we describe a case application of AI/ML methods (i.e., incorporating them into
2 new or existing applications) in human health environmental chemical assessments. Data
3 extraction is currently one of the most laborious steps in the workflow and typically conducted by a
4 PhD level scientist. Therefore Our objective is exploratory as we seek to understand the usability of
5 a new data extraction tool (Dexter) <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/34920276/>, a web-based
6 data extraction tool that provides a user-verification workflow of ML predictions for data entities)
7 in a chemical assessment workflow. In this exploratory case application, the goal is not to optimize
8 model performance, but to understand if the data extraction experience is improved with ML
9 models (assisted by humans) compared to a human only data extraction approach.

10 **2.0 METHODS**

11 This methodology focuses on the data extraction component of a chemical assessment
12 workflow (see Figure 1). This data extraction module will be used to conduct an evidence map
13 based on the template methods for a Provisional Peer-Reviewed Toxicity Value (PPRTV) as
14 described in (U.S. EPA, 2020)) and in accordance with the systematic review methods used to
15 conduct the SEMs as outlined in the Office of Research and Development (ORD) Staff Handbook for
16 Developing Integrated Risk Information (IRIS) Assessments (U.S. EPA, 2022). The specific methods
17 developing the SEM, including database searches, and collecting references, the Populations
18 Exposure, Comparator, and Outcome (PECO) criteria, and literature screening and tagging are
19 described in the Supplemental Material, Appendices A-D. The aim of this study was to understand
20 the usability of a new semi-automated data extraction tool, Dexter, in a chemical assessment
21 workflow. Dexter is a web-based, customized version of the Laser AI tool (<https://laser.ai>), a
22 systematic review tool based on AI. Dexter includes features that allow creation of customized data
23 extraction form templates with features such as ML models for data extraction of animal and
24 human health studies, with the additional options to include data extraction fields based on flat or
25 hierarchical vocabularies (picklists), and to relate data elements to each other. The underlying ML
26 models underlying the data extraction in Dexter (were originally developed as part of NIST-TAC
27 SRIE as described by (Nowake and Kunstman 2018 and Schmitt et al. 2018) with the additional
28 Dexter features as described by (Walker et. al., 2022).

1
 2 **Figure 1.** The workflow for conducting a chemical assessment is described on the left. The tools listed on
 3 the right support modules in that workflow, particularly those colored in the green boxes. EPA’s Health
 4 and Environmental Research Online (HERO) facilitates literatures searches and reference library
 5 management. Evidence Partner’s DistillerSR, and Sciome’s SWIFT-Active Screener and SWIFT-Review are
 6 useful literature screening and tagging tools. DistillerSR is also used for data extraction supporting SEM
 7 development. EPA Health Assessment Workplace Collaborative (HAWC) is the primary content
 8 management system for chemical assessments and facilitates reference, management, screening,
 9 literature tagging, data extraction and visualization. Tableau is typically used to make available SEM
 10 visuals. data and systematic review tools used within that workflow.

11 **2.1 Semi-automated Data Extraction**

12 **2.1.1 Data Extraction Strategy**

13 The ML models in Dexter were previously trained exclusively from the methods sections of
 14 open access literature, therefore the data extraction here will similarly be restricted to the methods
 15 sections of literature meeting full text screening criteria (see Appendix C for PECO criteria and
 16 Appendix D for screening and tagging). The data extraction module of the workflow will be divided
 17 into two study arms: manual data extraction (ME) and semi-automated data extraction (SE) as

1 depicted in Figure 2. The ME arm is designed to resemble the current review process with data
2 extracted by one team member and QC by a different team member [as outlined in the Office of
3 Research and Development (ORD) Staff Handbook for Developing Integrated Risk Information
4 (IRIS) Assessments (U.S. EPA, 2022) and in (Thayer et. al., 2022)]. In the ME arm, one of the data
5 extractors reads each study and manually extracts text from the methods section into the data
6 extraction fields (see Appendix E, Supplementary Tables 1 and 2). In the SE arm, one data extractor
7 reviews the model-generated data extractions and highlights. The data extractor makes corrections
8 if needed to the extracted data adding missing or removing extractions to fields as needed.

9 Both the ME and SE arms are implemented in Dexter using the fields described in Appendix
10 E, for animal toxicology studies (Supplemental Table 7) or human health studies (Supplemental
11 Table 8). The difference between the two arms and project set-up in Dexter is that there are no ML
12 models attached to the ME data extraction fields during project set-up. The MEs are also told to
13 manually highlight the relevant extracted text in the PDF during the extraction process to not only
14 facilitate QC, but also collect annotations that could be used for developing training data sets.

15 The results of extractions from ME and SE are then reviewed by two different quality
16 assurance (QA) reviewers. The QA reviewers will be blinded regarding study arm allocation.
17 To control for differences between extractors' performance, the same extractors participate both in
18 ME and SE study arms. For each extractor, the references assigned to them will be randomized
19 across ME and SE in a 1:1 ratio. No extractor will extract or review the same reference across both
20 arms. Each study arm has a separate Dextr project with identical data extraction forms and fields
21 with picklists enabled. The ME project will not have models attached to the fields in the data
22 extraction forms. To reduce variability associated with different levels of experience with the tool,
23 all reviewers will complete one hour training on how to use the tool and will be required to
24 perform extraction of two studies prior to starting the work. These two studies will not be included
25 in the metrics for data extraction or reviewer time. Team members are instructed to not remain idle
26 while signed into Dextr to ensure that accurate recording of the time to complete extractions is
27 logged (Dexter automatically records the time users take to complete tasks). The times between
28 start and stop actions will be manually checked against the event log in Dexter to ensure there were
29 no cases of an extraction task being left idle, inflating the overall extraction time. Additionally, the

1 user action logs from Dextr will be filtered for any periods of inactivity longer than 5 minutes and
 2 excluded from the calculation of time metrics. The data extractions will be exported from Dexter
 3 using the export feature. The HAWC client is used to import the datasets into the HAWC project
 4 (HAWC, 2023). All data will be available for download.

5

Manual Data Extraction Team (MET)	Human-in-the-Loop Data Extraction Team (HET)
Extractor 	
QA Reviewer 	

6

7 **Figure 1.** Data Extraction Teams. Two data extractors will independently extract data from
 8 references into forms using Dextr. The manual data extraction (ME) will manually extract all
 9 information while the semi-automated data extraction (SE) will manually extract all non-automated
 10 fields, while reviewing and correcting the model-generated extraction. Two different quality
 11 assurance (QA) reviewers will then correct both results for a given study to ensure accuracy of data
 12 extractions and calculate quality metrics.

13 **2.2 Evaluation of semi-automated data extraction in the SEM workflow**

14 The aim of the evaluation will be to understand how using the tool Dextr will perform as a
 15 semi-automated data extraction tool in an assessment workflow. The primary goals were to
 16 understand if the overall Dexter user experience was favorable and if the SE arm performed equal
 17 to or better than the ME arm. The evaluation will focus on the first pass data extraction, prior to QA

1 results will not be incorporated into the first pass model performance metrics due to the potential
2 to introduce complexity in resolving disagreements between reviewers.

3 First pass model performance will be evaluated manually and based on human review of
4 the primary results from Dexter. A collection of metrics that include recall, precision, and F-1 score
5 from selected data extraction fields from animal (test article name, species, strain, sex, and
6 endpoint) or human (study population source, chemical name, exposure measurement type) will be
7 evaluated initially. Results will be calculated by comparing the extracted data after primary
8 extraction within each data extraction arm. Precision is the number of correct positive predictions
9 made and is represented by the true positives/ (true positives + false positives). Recall quantifies
10 the number of correct positives made out of all correct positives that could have been made and is
11 represented by true positives/ (true positives + false negatives). The precision and recall score will
12 be combined into a single F measure (the harmonic mean or F1 score) for summarizing overall
13 model performance within a field. The F-measure will be calculated as $(2 * \text{precision} * \text{recall}) /$
14 $(\text{precision} + \text{recall})$.

15 The extracted data elements will be evaluated within an experimental arm for the number
16 of correct data points entered for a specific field (i.e. test article name) from the primary extraction
17 among all the primary extraction data points within a field. A data point will be marked as a “true
18 positive” if it matches with the same element in the primary extraction +QA (i.e. when the human
19 does not change the model response). A data point will be marked as a “false positive” if the
20 element is included in the primary extraction by the model, but not included in the primary
21 extraction +QA (i.e. a human makes a change to the model response). A data point will be marked as
22 a “false negative” if the element is missed by the model in the SE arm and included by human in the
23 manual extraction. A data point will be marked as a true negative when the model and the human
24 do not fill in a field. True negatives will be identified by comparing data extracts to gold standard
25 data available within HAWC ([ORD SEM PFAS 150 \(2022\) | HAWC \(epa.gov\)](https://www.epa.gov/hawc/ord-sem-pfas-150-2022)) and
26 <https://hawc.epa.gov/assessment/100500328/>.

27 The time metrics will be calculated both for the primary extraction and QA steps from both
28 arms to measure the total extraction time for comparing the manual vs semi-automated arms. Total
29 time for both the primary extraction as well as the time for QA will be evaluated.

1 **2.3 Usability Feedback**

2 After completing the data extraction, user experience will be qualitatively through
3 questionnaire (Appendix F, Supplemental Table 9).

4 **2.4 Data Storage**

5 All data generated by the workflow describe here will be stored in HAWC and HERO at
6 <https://hawc.epa.gov/assessment/100500328/> and
7 https://heronet.epa.gov/heronet/index.cfm/project/page/project_id/3591, respectively.

8 **2.5 Caveats and Limitations**

9 This study will include extraction of 20 papers previously extracted as the primary intent is
10 to evaluate the workflow (versus evaluation of model performance). Due to the novelty of the
11 application, plausible estimates of the effect values across time and accuracy metrics are unknown,
12 therefore formal sample size calculations are not provided, but are based on prior user and
13 developer experience with Dexter.

14 The study is designed to inform US EPA application of semi-automated extraction tools.
15 Hence, the workflow and data extraction forms resemble the ones used at US EPA. These conditions
16 may not apply elsewhere, so the study results may not generalize to all settings in which literature
17 reviews of environmental agents are performed.

18 Although not the primary goal of the current protocol, the manually curated results can be
19 incorporated back into the models to refine the model's performance and then redeployed in Dextr.
20 In subsequent projects, the new model performance can be reevaluated. Over time, it is expected
21 that model performance will improve given that more data are available for training. The
22 sustainable workflow is explicitly intended to include a human such that the workflow is semi-
23 automated and model performance can be evaluated and improved with routine use of ML-
24 facilitated data extraction over time.

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